

Polarized intensity (mJy beam⁻¹)

0.4

0.6

0.8

1.0

01

$z_{\text{sp}} = 0.37779$

55°01'30"

00"

00'30"

100 kpc

15^h56^m09^s 06^s

03^s

00^s

RA (J2000)

Dec (J2000)

